

THE WALL EFFECT ON MOLD FILLING IN RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

Mold filling in resin transfer molding is often treated as flow through porous media and Darcy's law is widely used as the framework for simulations and experiments. Darcy's law attributes the pressure gradient in the flow to the resistance of porous media, which is valid for large flow domains but may not be sufficient when the flow is restricted between containing walls. This paper discusses the wall effect on flow through porous media confined in a mold. A wall correction factor is introduced. The use of the wall correction factor is demonstrated in a mold filling simulation using scale modeling.

KEY WORDS: Flow, Porous media, Wall Effect, Resin Transfer Molding, Darcy's law, Mold Filling, Simulation, Scaling, Permeability, Composites.

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) has been increasingly recognized as an alternative composite manufacturing technology to replace the expensive autoclave curing-prepreg method. RTM has great potential for high volume and high speed production but the quality of the RTM products is still inferior as compared with those by autoclave method. One of the key stages directly related to product quality in RTM is mold filling. Improper resin flow pattern can leave defects such as dry spots and voids in composites. Mold filling has been the subject of many researches.

Mold filling stage in resin transfer molding is often treated as flow through porous media and Darcy's law is widely used as the framework for various mold filling modeling, simulations and experimental measurements. Darcy's law attributes the pressure drop in the flow to the resistance of porous media. This is sufficient in applications such as petroleum engineering, soil mechanics and ground water hydrology[1,2], where the characteristic length of flow domain is far more larger than the order of the permeability of porous media. In RTM, however, the flow of fluid is confined in a mold where the characteristic length of flow domain may be relatively small and hence the constraint effect of mold wall on flow may not be negligible.

This paper discusses the wall effect on the flow of a fluid through a porous medium confined in an impermeable mold. The friction caused by mold wall is considered following Brinkman's equation. A correction factor accounting for wall effect on pressure gradient is introduced. The use of the correction factor is demonstrated in a mold filling simulation using scale modeling.

ANALYSIS

The flow of a fluid through a porous medium is commonly described by Darcy's law:

$$v_0 = - \frac{K}{\mu} (\nabla P - \rho g) \quad (1)$$

where v_0 is the superficial velocity, K is the permeability of the porous medium, μ is the viscosity, P is the pressure, ρ is the density of the fluid and g is the gravitational acceleration. In permeability measurement and simplified mold filling simulations, the average velocity \bar{v}_0 is actually used and the effect of velocity profile near the mold wall is neglected.

The velocity profiles near containing walls for flow through porous media may be considered following an empirical modification of Darcy's law proposed by Brinkman [3]:

$$-\nabla P - \frac{\mu}{K} v_0 + \mu \nabla^2 v_0 + \rho g = 0 \quad (2)$$

For the flow through a narrow slit formed by two parallel walls with a distance $2B$ apart and filled with a porous material of uniform permeability K , as shown in Fig.1, Brinkman's equation becomes

$$0 = - \frac{dP}{dz} - \frac{\mu}{K} v_0 + \mu \frac{d^2 v_0}{dx^2} \quad (3)$$

With a boundary condition $v_0 = 0$ at $x = \pm B$, the velocity distribution in the porous medium is found:

$$v_0 = - \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dz} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}}\right)} \right) \quad (4)$$

and the average velocity in the slit is

$$\bar{v}_0 = - \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dz} \left(1 - \frac{\sinh\left(\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}{\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}} \cosh\left(\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}}\right)} \right) \quad (5)$$

Eqn (5) indicates that to account for the wall effect, a correction factor α needs to be introduced into Darcy's equation:

$$\bar{v}_0 = - \frac{K}{\mu} (\nabla P - \rho g) \alpha \quad (6)$$

with

$$\alpha = \alpha_B \alpha_W = \left(1 - \frac{\sinh\left(\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}{\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}} \cosh\left(\frac{B}{\sqrt{K}}\right)} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sinh\left(\frac{W}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}{\frac{W}{\sqrt{K}} \cosh\left(\frac{W}{\sqrt{K}}\right)} \right) \quad (7)$$

for a rectangular mold with a cavity thickness $2B$ and width $2W$.

For a tube of radius R, the α is obtained following the solution given by [3]

$$\alpha = \left(1 - 2 \frac{I_1\left(\frac{R}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}{\frac{R}{\sqrt{K}} I_0\left(\frac{R}{\sqrt{K}}\right)}\right) \quad (8)$$

where I_0 and I_1 are Bessel functions.

Fig.2 plots the correction factor α versus B/\sqrt{K} . As seen, the wall effect is significant in the range of $B/\sqrt{K} < 20$. This happens in some permeability measurements where the mold cavity thickness is relatively small and/or the permeability is high. The wall correction factor presented in this paper would be useful to account the effect of mold size when comparing permeability data obtained from different laboratories. α is less than 1% when $B/\sqrt{K} > 100$. Therefore the wall effect becomes negligible when the permeability is low and/or the thickness of the mold cavity is relatively larger.

CASE STUDY: SCALE SIMULATION OF MOLD FILLING IN RTM

Scale modeling of mold filling in RTM has been studied aiming at to provide a means of experimentation on a small mold before a large, expensive mold is to be built [4]. The agreement between the scale analysis and experiments, however, was not very satisfactory. In this paper, the scale relations are reexamined with the wall correction factor.

SCALE RELATIONS WITH THE WALL CORRECTION FACTOR

For an isothermal RTM mold filling process, the following seven variables were considered to be relevant to scale analysis [4]:

- q_0 = the inlet resin flow rate, L/t.
- K = the preform permeability, L^2 .
- μ = the resin dynamic viscosity, M/Lt.
- ΔP = the pressure difference between two points, M/Lt²
- L = a characteristic length of mold dimension, L.
- t = the mold filling time t, t.
- e = the thickness of the boundary layer, accounting for the non-uniform fiber distribution near mold wall, L.

The dimensional analysis has yielded the following dimensionless groups

$$\pi_1 = \frac{\Delta PK}{\mu q_0 L}, \quad \pi_2 = \frac{q_0 t}{L}, \quad \pi_3 = \frac{K}{L^2}, \quad \pi_4 = \frac{e}{L} \quad (9)$$

and hence the functional relation

$$\frac{\Delta PK}{\mu q_0 L} = F\left(\frac{q_0 t}{L}, \frac{K}{L^2}, \frac{e}{L}\right) \quad (10)$$

The exact form of F is to be determined by scale experiments. Because it is not convenient to correlate Eqn (10) to experimental data, a simplified functional relation has been used in previous study [5]:

$$\frac{\Delta PK}{\mu q_0 L} = F\left(\frac{q_0 t}{L}\right) \quad (11)$$

Eqn (11) is valid when $K \ll L^2$ and $e \ll L$, i.e. the mold is considered sufficiently large as compared to the value of K and size of the boundary layer. This is, however, not the case in many RTM processes.

With the knowledge of wall correction factor, the contribution of π_3 can be considered separately from that of π_2 and π_4 . Neglect the effect of π_4 , Eqn (10) becomes

$$\alpha \frac{\Delta PK}{\mu q_0 L} = F\left(\frac{q_0 t}{L}\right) \quad (12)$$

Eqn (12) is a more general equation and yet retains a simple form.

The scale factors have been defined as the following [4]:

$$S_L = \frac{L_1}{L_2}, \quad S_P = \frac{\Delta P_1}{\Delta P_2}, \quad S_q = \frac{q_{01}}{q_{02}}, \quad S_\mu = \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2}, \quad S_t = \frac{t_1}{t_2}, \quad S_K = \frac{K_1}{K_2} \quad (13)$$

and the scale laws are

$$S_P S_K = S_\mu S_q S_L \quad \text{and} \quad S_L = S_q S_t \quad (14)$$

To account for the wall effect, a wall scale factor should be added:

$$S_\alpha = \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \quad (15)$$

and the scale laws become

$$S_\alpha S_P S_K = S_\mu S_q S_L \quad \text{and} \quad S_L = S_q S_t \quad (16)$$

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Scale tests have been conducted previously with a 2-D mold filling simulation set-up. Fiberglass mat was used as preform and motor oil was used as the filling fluid. Tests were conducted on two 2-D mold geometry shapes, one is I-shape and another has irregular shape, as shown in Fig.3. For each mold shape, two geometrically similar molds with a size scale factor $S_L = 2$ were investigated. The dimensions given in Fig.3 are for the larger molds. Experimental details have been described previously [5]. Table 1 presents the experimental parameters used and characteristic values obtained for several tests. The wall correction factors corresponding to each test are also listed.

Functional Relation

According to the simplified functional relation Eqn (11), the data obtained from the same mold shape should follow the same curve when plotted as π_1 versus π_2 . Figs.4 and 5 present such plots obtained from the irregular mold shape and I-shape mold for two mold sizes, respectively; a and b in Figs.4 and 5 correspond to the pressure measured at points P1 and P2 (indicated in Fig.3), respectively. It can be seen that, when plotted in dimensionless form, the data from two mold sizes displayed the similar curve shape but did not fall on to the same curve. The π_1 values from the small mold were always higher than that of large mold and their discrepancy accumulated as mold filling progressed.

Figs.6 and 7 plot the same set of data again following Eqn (12). As seen, when the wall effect was corrected, the data from two mold sizes fell onto the same curve for irregular mold shape. For I-shape mold, the difference between the data from two mold sizes was also much reduced.

Scale Law

Using the scale laws, one can predict the unknown scale factors from the known scale factors and hence estimate the unknown processing parameters from the results of model tests. In the present study, the pressure scale factor S_p and the time scale factor S_t are the unknowns. In Table 2 the scale factors for tests listed in Table 1 are compared with the predictions by scale laws using both Eqn (14) (without wall correction) and Eqn (16) (with wall correction). With wall correction, the largest error for S_p value prediction is reduced from 51% to 10%.

TABLE 1 EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS FOR SCALE TESTS

Mold Type and Size	V_f^a	K ($\times 10^{-9}m^2$)	μ (Pa-s)	q_0 ($\times 10^{-2}m/s$)	P_{max}^b (KPa)	t_{fill}^c (sec)	α_B	α_W
I-shape large	0.144	4.735	0.520	0.169	114	150	0.81	0.99
I-shape small	0.131	5.599	0.413	0.243	84	50	0.61	0.96
irregular large	0.141	4.897	0.556	0.166	97	145	0.81	0.99
irregular small	0.136	5.245	0.453	0.220	64	55	0.63	0.98

a: V_f = fiber volume fraction. b: P_{max} = the maximum pressure measured at point P1, see Fig.3. c: t_{fill} = the filling time for mold cavity with preform

TABLE 2 COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS WITH PREDICTIONS BY SCALE LAW

	Experiment*	Scale law Eqn (14)	Error	Scale law Eqn (16)	Error
I-shape mold					
$S_L=2, S_{q0}=0.695$	$S_p=1.37$	$S_p=2.07$	51.2%	$S_p=1.51$	10.2%
$S_K=0.846, S_\mu=1.26$	$S_t = 3.00$	$S_t = 2.88$	- 4.0%	-	-
irregular mold					
$S_L=2, S_{q0}=0.750$	$S_p=1.52$	$S_p= 1.96$	28.9%	$S_p=1.51$	-0.7%
$S_K=0.940, S_\mu=1.23$	$S_t = 2.64$	$S_t = 2.67$	1.3%	-	-

* S_p is calculated based on the P_{max} measured at point P1 while S_t is calculated based on the time needed for filling the preform.

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Figure 1 Flow through a slit.

Figure 2 The wall correction factor for a slit-shape mold.

Figure 3 2-D geometries used for scale tests, (a) irregular shape mold; (b) I-shape mold. (All dimensions in mm)

Figure 4 π_1 as a function of π_2 measured by scale experiment with the irregular shape mold for two mold sizes with a size scale factor $S_L=2$. The reference starting time ($t=0$) is chosen when flow front reached P_1 . The pressure was measured at point (a) P_1 ; (b) P_2 . (\square) for large mold and (\circ) for small mold.

Figure 5 π_1 as a function of π_2 measured by scale experiment with the I-shape mold for two mold sizes with a size scale factor $S_L=2$. The reference starting time ($t=0$) is chosen when flow front reached P_1 . The pressure was measured at point (a) P_1 ; (b) P_2 . (□) for large mold and (O) for small mold.

Figure 6 $\alpha \pi_1$ as a function of π_2 for the irregular shape mold; notations are as in Fig.4.

Figure 7 $\alpha \pi_1$ as a function of π_2 for the I-shape mold; notations are as in Fig.5.